

SAVINGS AND INVESTMENT PATTERN OF ACADEMICIANS IN COIMBATORE CITY, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

¹Dr.R.Sathich ²Dr. I. Haroon Basha ³Mrs. J. Smruthymol ⁴Dr. Fasahat Nazir Buchoo

ABSTRACT

The goal of the current investigation is to Analyze professors' investment and savings habits.. 200 respondents provided the core data for this investigation. Statistical methods such as the chi-square test and factor analysis have been employed to examine the information gathered from the participants. And the researcher has found saving and investment pattern academicians the information regarding Most academicians influences the factors of safety, liquidity, children's career, and feature benefits for these purposes, it has also been found that the Many academicians Invest in gold, life insurance, post office savings plans, and bank deposits.

Key words: Investment Avenues, Academicians

1 Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, AMET University , Chennai.

2 Assistant Professor, AMET Business School, AMET University , Chennai.

3 Assistant Professor , Department of Commerce , Karpagam Academy of Higher Education , Coimbatore.

4 Assistant Professor , AMET Business School, AMET University , Chennai.

INTRODUCTION

The bank provided investment options (savings accounts, fixed deposits, recurring deposits, and current accounts), life insurance policies, post office modest savings plans, chit funds, real estate, mutual funds, gold, shares, debentures, and commodity markets etc. When it comes to investing, everyone has different investment preferences. the influence of his/her own environment. investment avenue that generates a high return over time and at a certain level of risk differential This study examines the methods for conserving and investment patterns of academicians in Coimbatore city.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. G. Ravindran and M. Yasodha¹ (2015) Teachers' Savings and Investing Behavior in Arts and Science Colleges In the present world, everyone needs money. Everyone needs to be financially secure in order to live a happy and tranquil life. India's economy is among the fastest expanding in the world, with a greater GDP. In order to go to the top, effective money management is now essential for boosting additional economic growth. Appropriate savings and investments can help achieve this. Savings funds ought to be allocated to suitable investment vehicles. At the gross root level, investments and savings help the entire economy in addition to a single individual.

Ms. K J Anju and Anuradha P S (2015) Review and Agenda for Future Research on Saving and Investing Behavior: In recent years, the financial services sector has become incredibly varied.giving investors a wide range of investing choices. Financial planning and prudent investing strategies can enhance an investor's personal wealth while also contributing to economic prosperity. A country's rate of economic growth is one of the key factors affecting the standard of living of its people. An economy's growth is measured using three key indicators: income, savings, and investments. In order to determine investor behavior, this study reanalyses a wide range of international literature. An interpretive approach has been used to assess the study's objectives, sample, research methods, and findings in order to support further research. To create a strong conceptual foundation for the researchers, this study closely looks at the experimental studies on investor behavior conducted in various countries. The study illustrates how a broad

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The current study's only goal is to find out what academics in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, think about their saving and investing habits.

METHODOLOGY

The district of Coimbatore is Tamil Nadu's Manchester. The study was carried out by the authors among 200 academicians in Coimbatore city, with a focus on their saving and investment habits. The information used in this study was gathered from the academicians who gathered at arts and science colleges on different days. Since an education institution will come forward to give permission to conduct research among its academicians, the authors have made this different attempt. It is to be noted here that during the study period there were around 10 arts and science colleges in the study area. For collecting the primary data, the authors had employed some trained investigators. The study was conducted by the end of May; 2023. The authors have adopted convenience sampling methods to collect the original information. A systematic questionnaire was used to gather the primary data. Questionnaire contained closed end question only. Multiple choice questions were also included. Besides this five-point scaling techniques has also been employed in the questionnaire. The SPSS software was used to process, analyze, and tabulate the data that were gathered. The data has been analyzed using a straightforward percentage method. Moreover, factor analysis and the chi-square test have been employed to support or refute the association between various investment paths.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The opinion elicited from the academicians in the sample area may or may not be applicable to the other areas.
2. The study has been conducted only among the academicians of arts and science colleges and not among engineering, medical, education and other colleges in the study area.

ANALYTICAL PART OF THE STUDY

It is assumed that there is an inter relationship between the profile of the academicians and their perceived opinion. Keeping this in mind, in this part an attempt has been made to

present the profile of the sample academician in Coimbatore city and is given in the table that follows.

TABLE .1

The age range of the participants

(In years) Age	Number of Respondents	%
Below 25	27	13.5
26 to 30	25	12.5
31 to 40	118	59.0
Above 41	30	15.0
Overall	200	100.0

Source: Primary data

The above mentioned Table indicates that, of the 200 sample respondents in total, 59.0% are between the ages of 31 and 40, 15.0% are over 41, 13.5% are under 25 years old, and another 12.5% are between the ages of 26 and 30. Therefore, it may be inferred that a significant proportion of sample respondents fall between the 31 to 40 year age range.

TABLE 2

The respondents' gender

Sex	Number of Respondents	%
Boy	146	73.0
Girl	54	27.0
Overall	200	100.0

Source: Primary data

Table 2 above, which displays the gender distribution of the sample respondents, indicates that 27.0% of respondents are female and 73.0% of respondents are male. It follows that men are more inclined than women to invest and save money.

Marital Status of the Respondents.

The following Table lists the sample respondents' marital status.

3 TABLE

Status of the Respondents' Marriage

Status Of Marriage	Number of the Respondents	%
Married	119	59.5
Unmarried	81	40.5
Overall	200	100

Source: Primary data

The 200 sample respondents, as indicated in Table 3 above, are split 49.5% married and 50.5 percent single. Therefore, the majority of responses are likely married.

TABLE 4

The educational background of the participants

Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
PG with Ph.D	40	20.0
PG NET	21	10.5
PG with SET	112	56.0
PG	27	13.5
Overall	200	100

Source: Primary data

Based on the above Table, which indicates that 56.0% of respondents are PG with SET, 20.0% are PG with Ph.D., 13.5% are PG, and 10.5% are PG with NET, we can infer that a significant number of the 200 sample respondents are PG with SET.

TABLE 5
Employment Situation of the Participants

Occupational Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Private Institutions	182	90.6
Government Institution	18	9.4
Overall	200	100

Primary data source

The respondent's occupation is shown in the above Table. Given that 90.6 percent of the 200 sample respondents are private college institutions and 9.4 % are government college institutions, it may be inferred that a substantial portion of the respondents are private college institutions.

TABLE 6
Income Per Year for the Respondents

(In)Annual Income	Number of Respondents	%
150000 to 200000	10	5.0
210000 to 300000	106	53.0
310000 to 400000	65	35.5
Above 410000	19	9.5
Overall	200	100

Primary data source

Table 6 displays the responses from the 200 sample members, 53.0 percent fall within the annual income group of < 21,0000 – 30,0000, 35.5 percent fall within the annual income group of ~31,0000 – 40,0000, 5.0 percent fall within the annual income group of ~ 15,0000 – 20,0000, and 9.5 percent fall within the annual income group of above ~41,0000. It may be inferred that 53.0% of the participants fall into the <21, 0000 – 0, 0000 annual income bracket.

TABLE 7
Age and Safety purpose

ages	Completely Concur	Accept	Indifferent	Contradict	Vehementlydisagree	Overall
Below 25	18	6	1	2	0	27
26 to 30	7	6	0	12	0	25
31 to 40	28	67	13	10	0	118
Above 41	7	2	6	9	6	30
Total	60	81	20	33	6	200

Source: Computed from Primary At 5% significant level

Table 7 shows that the chi-square value with 12 degrees of freedom is 99.233 and the P value is 0.00. Since the P value is less than 5%, the hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that the factors influencing safety and the respondents' ages are related, with respondents between the ages of 31 and 40 having a major influence on safety. The ages of the responders and the factors influencing safety are therefore correlated.

Gender and children career

In this section, the researcher attempts to determine whether the respondents' gender and the factors influencing their children's careers are related. Thus, the chi-square test has been used to develop and test a hypothesis.

Ho: There is no relationship between the respondents' factors influencing the gender of their offspring and their professional success..

TABLE 7
Gender and Children Career

Gender	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Total
Male	47	63	29	7	146
Female	1	45	2	6	54
Total	48	108	31	13	200

Source: Computed from Primary At 5% significant level

Three degrees of freedom, a P value of 0.00, and a chi-square value of 35.967 are shown in Table 7. Because the P value is smaller than 5%, the null hypothesis is rejected. This is a correlation between the respondents' gender and their impact on children's careers. In nutshell, is no similarity is found between the male and female respondents on factors influencing of children career. The frequency distribution also reveals that when compared to female gender the factors influencing is high among the male gender.

TABLE 8
Factor Influencing Saving and Investment Pattern of Academician

Elements	Firmly Concur	Concur	Impartial	Contradict	Very disapproving	Overall
Safety Purpose	60 (30.0)	81 (40.5)	20 (10.0)	33 (16.5)	6 (3.0)	200 (100)
Liquidity	120 (60.0)	74 (37.0)	-	-	6 (3.0)	200 (100)
Tax Saving Schemes	80 (40.0)	66 (33.0)	47 (23.5)	1 (.5)	6 (3.0)	200 (100)
Diversification	45 (22.5)	95 (47.5)	45 (22.5)	8 (4.0)	7 (3.5)	200 (100)
Good return	57 (28.5)	113 (56.5)	30 (15.0)	-	-	200 (100)
Capital appreciation	82 (41.0)	70 (35.0)	42 (21.0)	6 (3.0)	-	200 (100)
Children career	48 (24.0)	108 (54.0)	31 (15.5)	13 (6.5)	-	200 (100)
Features benefits	91 (45.5)	75 (37.5)	22 (11.0)	12 (6.0)	-	200 (100)

Source : Primary data

Safety purpose

Among the 200 sample participants, 40.5% expressed agreement, 30.0% strongly agreed, 10.0% were indifferent, 16.5% disagreed, and 3.0% strongly disagreed.

Liquidity

Regarding the factor "liquidity," 60.0% of respondents highly agree, 37.0% agree, and 3.0% strongly disagree.

Tax saving schemes

40.0% highly agree, 33.0% agree, 23% are neutral, 5.0 percent disagree, and 3.0 percent strongly disagree of the 200 sample participants.

Diversification

Of the 200 responders in the survey, 47% agree, 22.5 strongly agree, 22.5 are neutral, 4.0 disagree, and 3.5 strongly disagree with the statement "diversification."

Good Returns

28.0 percent of the 200 sample respondents strongly agree, 56.5 percent agree, and 15.0 percent are neutral.

Capital Appreciation

Of the 200 sample responders, 41.0 percent strongly agree, 35% agree, 21.0 percent are neutral, and 3.0 percent disagree with the component "capital appreciation."

Children Career

Of the 200 responders in the survey, 54.0% agree, 24% strongly agree, 15.0% are neutral, and 6.5% disagree.

Feature Benefits

Regarding the element "feature benefits," of the 200 sample respondents, 45.5% strongly agree, 37.5% agree, 11.0 percent are indifferent, and 6.0 percent disagree.

TABLE 9

Opinion of the Investment Avenues

Investment avenues	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Shares	95 (47.5)	81 (40.5)	12(6.0)	12(6.0)	-
Bank Deposits	43 (21.5)	62 (31.0)	64 (32.0)	25 (12.5)	6 (3.0)
Real estate	67 (33.5)	57 (28.5)	51 (25.5)	19 (9.5)	6 (3.0)
Mutual funds	55 (27.5)	53(26.5)	55 (27.5)	25 (12.5)	12 (6.0)
Debentures	42 (21.0)	61 (30.5)	63 (31.5)	21 (10.5)	13 (6.5)
Gold	62 (31.0)	86 (43.0)	31 (15.5)	20 (10.0)	1 (.5)
Life Insurance policies	61 (30.5)	43 (21.5)	61 (30.5)	27 (13.5)	8 (4.0)
Commodity market	60 (30.0)	57 (28.5)	61 (30.5)	20 (10.0)	2 (1.0)
Chit funds	44 (22.0)	42 (21.0)	70 (35.0)	38 (19.0)	6 (3.0)
Post office small savings, schemes	50 (25.0)	63 (31.5)	43 (21.5)	32 (16.0)	12 (6.0)

Source: Primary data

Shares

Of the 200 responders in the survey, 47.5% strongly agree, 40.0% agree, 6.0 percent are indifferent, and 605.1 percent disagree.

Bank Deposits

When it comes to the topic of "bank deposits," twenty percent of respondents strongly disagree, thirty percent agree, thirty two percent are indifferent, and fifteen percent disagree.

Real Estate

200 responders in the sample, 33.5% strongly agree, 28.5% agree, 25.5% are neutral, 9.5% disagree, and 3.0% strongly disagree.

Mutual Funds

Regarding the factor "mutual funds," of the 200 respondents in the sample, 27.5% strongly agree, 26.5% agree, 22.5 percent are neutral, 12.5% disagree, and 6.0 percent disagree significantly.

Debentures

Of the 200 respondents in the sample, 21 percent strongly agree, 35 percent agree, 31 percent are neutral, 10 percent disagree, and 6 percent disagree severely.

Gold

Of the 200 sample responders, 43% agree, 15.0 are neutral, 10.0 disagree, and 5.0 severely disagree with the factor "gold." Of them, 31.0 highly agree.

Life Insurance

Of the 200 sample responders, 35 percent strongly agree, 21 percent agree, 35 percent are neutral, 13 percent disagree, and 4 percent strongly disagree.

Commodity Market

Among the 200 respondents in the survey, 30.0 percent highly agree, 28.5 percent agree, 30.5 percent are neutral, 10.0 percent disagree, and 1.0 percent strongly disagree with the factor "commodity market."

Chit Funds

Nineteen percent disagree, three percent strongly disagree, twenty percent agree, thirty percent are neutral, and twenty-three percent strongly agree of the 200 sample responders.

Postal Savings Schemes

Regarding the factor "postal savings schemes," of the 200 respondents in the sample, 25.5% strongly agree, 31.5% agree, 21.5% are neutral, 16.0% disagree, and 6.0% strongly disagree.

TABLE 11
Bartlett's Test, KMO, likewise Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha		
Adequacy of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sampling Measures		.773
Bartlett's Sphericity Test	Approx. Chi-Square	895.932
	Df	45
	Sig.	.000

Source: Computed from Primary Data

The results of the Bartlett's test for investor attitude, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling measure, and Cronbach's alpha are displayed in Table 11. The degree to which the various components of an investor's attitude are consistent with each other and the degree to which measurement error occurs in each measure are both indicated by reliability. The eleven factors that were added together to produce a trustworthy scale of attitude for individual investors' score were evaluated using Cronbach's alpha. Each of the eleven items has an alpha co-efficient of 0.855. (should be higher than 0.7), indicating that the scale's items form a reasonable internal consistency reliable basis. The sample adequacy KMO value is 0.773, which is higher than the conventional norm of 0.5. It shows that each factor may be supported by a sufficient number of objects. The results of Bartlett's sphericity test showed a chi square value of 895.932, which is statistically significant at the one percent level. It guarantees that there is a strong enough correlation between the components to give factor analysis a solid foundation.

12 TABLE
Factor Analysis: Investment Avenues

Investment Avenues	Rotated Factor Loading			Factor Name
	F1	F2	F3	
Mutual Funds	0.857			Savings
Gold	0.821			
Chit Funds	0.807			
Post office small savings schemes	0.696			
Bank Deposits	0.675			High Return and Risk
Debentures		0.873		
Commodity market		0.778		
Real Estate		0.611		
Share		0.865		Policies
Life insurance policies			0.739	
% of variance	32.653	20.557	17.248	
Cumulative %	32.653	52.210	17.248	

Note: Primary component analysis is the extraction approach.
It rotates using Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
Source: computed using the actual data

The items are condensed into a small number of variables using factor analysis. The factor analysis results for investment avenue information are displayed in Table 12. Three components comprise a proven item on investing avenue. Three factors that account for 52.20% of the variance among the eleven items were discovered to be greater than leigenvalue. Bank deposits (0.675), gold (0.821), chit funds (0.807), mutual funds (0.857), and post office small savings plans (0.696) are highly correlated with factor 1 savings avenue. Debentures (0.873), the commodity market (0.778), real estate (0.611), shares (0.865), and life insurance policies (0.739) are highly correlated with factor 2 high return and risk avenue.

FINDINGS

1. It is clearly shown that academicians aged 31 to 40 years are interested in making an investment of 59.0 per cent of them.
2. The category of respondents comprised 74.0 percent males.
3. 59.5 Per cent of the respondent are married
4. Investment rather than savings 56.0 percent of those polled are PG with SET.
5. Of the 200 participants, 90.5% of the participants work for private companies. We can conclude that those with salaries have different investment beliefs.
6. Research reveals that the majority of academics work for certain institutions. Of those surveyed, 53.0% earn between Rs. 21,0000 and Rs. 30,0000 annually.
7. The investigation reveals that several elements impact the "safety purpose". Of those surveyed, 40.5% concur that "liquidity" 60.0% of those surveyed strongly concur that "tax saving schemes" Forty percent of the participants firmly concur that "Diversification" Of the respondents, 47% concur that "good returns" 28.0% of those surveyed said they strongly agreed. "Capital appreciation"41.0% of those surveyed strongly concur with "children's career." 54.0% of those surveyed concur that "feature benefits" 45.5% of those surveyed said they strongly agreed.
8. It is shown that 47.5% of respondents strongly agree that "shares" is an investment route. Twenty-one percent of the respondents strongly agree with "bank deposits". 33.5 percent of respondents strongly agreed with "real estate," 27.5 percent strongly agreed with

"mutual funds," and 7.5 percent strongly agreed with "debentures." 31.5 percent say they are unsure or disagree. "Gold" 43.0% of those surveyed concur that "Life Insurance" Thirty-five percent of respondents are neutral toward "Child Funds," thirty-five percent strongly agree with "Commodity markets," and thirty-five percent are neutral toward "Postal savings schemes." 31.5% of those surveyed said they agree.

CONCLUSION

In life, money plays a more significant role. With the right investment, people's quality of life rises. For these reasons, the majority of academicians have an impact on the variables of safety, liquidity, children's career, and feature benefits. Scholars are frugal with their finances. Most of their income is invested in shares, which are high-risk but highly profitable ventures. A lot of academics make investments in gold, life insurance, post office savings plans, and bank accounts. The following scholars don't take on risk at a reasonable rate of return when making these kinds of investments. Few academics know that they can invest in commodities markets and mutual funds. Before receiving advice from a financial advisor or share broker, academicians may invest in stocks, mutual funds for the commodities market, or the stock market itself.

References

- [1] ParimalaKanthi, Dr M. Ashok Kumar 2015. "A Study on Investment Preference and Behaviour of Investment Investors in Coimbatore",Bonfring International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Science.
- [2] Muthumeenakshi 2017. "Perception of Investors towards the Investment Pattern on Different Investment Avenues – A Review", Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce, JIBC.
- [3] Dr. T. Sisili, S. Gokul Kumar, S. Siva kumar.2018. "A study on Investors behaviour over Investment Options". IJARIE.
- [4] Satish Singh, Anuj Sheopuri, Mohammad Sajid 2019." Investment Behaviour and Awareness Among Teachers of Private College", Innovare Journal of Business Management.
- [5] Amandeep Kaur, Ramanjot Kaur .2020. "A Study of Saving and Investment Pattern of Individuals with Special Reference to Ludhiana District", International Journal Management and Social Science.
- [6] Haroon Basha. I (2015), Green promotion : A study on its Impact towards the Business and Environmental Protection ,IJABM,Vol.3,No.1,pp:222-227. (ISSN: 2289-4519).
- [7] Haroon Basha . I (2019), REVIEW ON SECURITY AND PRIVACY MANAGEMENT, IJMTE ,Vol.6 , Issue.3 , pp :1305 -1309, (ISSN: 2249-7455) (UGC Approved)
- [8] Haroon Basha. I et al., (2016), THE DOMAIN ONTOLOGY DRIVEN SYSTEMS: GROWTH AND CHALLENGES, Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Science (AJBAS), Vol. 10, No. 12, pp: 300-306.

- [9] Mehfooza Munavar, Pattabiraman .V (2013). Assessment of Surface Water Quality in Muttukadu Coastal Regions, Chennai of Southern India using Factor Analysis, International Journal of Oceans and Oceanography, Vol. 7, No. 2, pp: 131-141.
- [10] Mehfooza Munavar, Pattabiraman .V (2014). Identification of Water Quality by Principal Component and Spatial Cluster Analysis Methods in Muttukadu Coastal Regions, Chennai of Southern India, published in the International Journal, Ecology, Environment and Conservation, Vol. 1, No. 20, pp: 87-96.
- [11] Mehfooza Munavar, Pattabiraman .V (2013). A Methodology Adopted towards Analysis of Spatial Patterns of Chlorophyll Distribution in Coastal Areas, International Journal of Computer Applications & Information Technology, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp: 20-24.